

Organ of Corti Vibration Measurements for Hearing Aid Applications

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Abstract. A hallmark of the mammalian cochlea is high sensitivity, sharp tuning, and level dependent non-linear gain, which is thought to be due to outer hair cell (OHC) electro-motility. OHC damage decreases cochlear sensitivity and renders the cochlea linear that manifests as auditory pathologies. Hearing aids are designed to restore level dependent non-linear cochlear motion lost due to OHC damage. The most successful hearing aids use frequency-dependent band compression algorithms that provide more gain at low levels and less at high levels. This multi-band compression strategy is consistent with previously measured basilar membrane measurements from the basal high frequency region. Recent measurements of the organ of Corti (OoC) using optical coherence tomography (OCT) from the mid and low frequency regions below about 3 kHz, important for speech, suggests a different strategy. We measured OoC displacements at the gerbil 2 kHz region for the normal ear, and after applying a 2 kHz and then 4 kHz high level tone exposure. This is towards the goal of understanding amplification strategies using an animal model for hearing aids.

INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

Modern hearing aids use multiband compression where for a given frequency band, the gain prescribed depends on the input level and is thus non-linear [1]. The prescribed gain also depends on the degree of hearing loss with the goal of restoring normal loudness. A proxy for understanding the effects of hearing amplification is to measure cochlear motion which determines auditory nerve input. How well the motion of the damaged cochlea is restored to levels of a healthy cochlea with a hearing aid, has not been physiologically tested. Part of the reason for this is that it had been difficult to make in vivo measurements in intact animals, and nearly impossible in humans. The recent development of OCT for in vivo measurements allows measurements of the intact cochlea of several animal models ([2], [3], [4]). In this study we aimed to measure and compare the mechanical responses of healthy cochlea, and after tone induced hearing loss, using OCT. We used the gerbil as an animal model and made measurements in the 2 kHz speech frequency region.

METHODS

Healthy gerbils ranging in age from 5 – 8 weeks were used. The surgery of animals was carried out as approved by Mass. Eye and Ear protocols and methods described previously [1]. After performing the surgery, the middle ear cavity was exposed by opening bulla by the application of PAG (phosphoric acid gel), and cochlear turns were identified using the stapedial artery as a reference (Fig. 1 A). Since, the main objective for this study was to evaluate the effects of acoustic amplification in the speech region, all

measurements were carried out in the second turn with a characteristic frequency of approximately 2 kHz. B-scan imaging and A-line motion measurements were made through the intact bony cochlea using OCT. The OCT head was mounted on a robot arm which allowed manipulations of the OCT beam and positioning to make measurements from a radial approach. The OCT beam angle was adjusted where OHCs, RL and Tunnel of Corti could be identified (Fig. 1B). In this view, an A-line allowed motion measurements of the OHC region as well as other nearby structures along a vertical axis (Fig 1 B).

Multi-point A-line displacement measurements with pure-tone stimuli with frequencies ranging from 1500 Hz – 3000 Hz were made for four different conditions: (1) the normal OoC with levels ranging from 30 – 90 dB SPL. (2) After a 4 kHz, and then (3) a 2 kHz tone stimulus each at 110 dB for 10 minutes to determine their possible effects on cochlear damage, and (4) postmortem all with input stimulation in the 80-100 dB SPL range.

Post-processing scripts in Matlab (2023) allowed extraction of single point measurements at individual locations from the multi-point A-line measurements. The location for the OHC region was identified from the B-scan and then, the depth location within that range was selected as representative location for OHCs. A noise rejection criterion was applied and only those measurements that were at least 6 dB above the noise floor at that location were analyzed. The radial displacement response at this depth for all frequencies and input SPL were analyzed. The output responses were normalized and expressed as dB relative to 1 nm. Several animals were used for practice, and results from only one gerbil with healthy hearing i.e. gain saturation are presently reported.

FIGURE 1. (A) A view of middle ear cavity through an opening in the bulla cavity wall. Gray line marks the location of stapedial artery used as a reference to identify the 3 turns of the cochlea indicated by blue lines. Back part of the tympanic membrane is visible in the foreground. Red arrow shows the location for the image scan in the 2nd turn. (B) OCT B-scan image of the cochlear middle turn through the otic capsule (bright red near the top). Tunnel of Corti is identified by the red triangle, blue (dashed) rectangle shows the OHC region.

RESULTS

The OHC displacement (dB re. 1 nm) measurements as a function of input level and frequency are summarized in Figure 2 as 3D plots. Figure 3 shows the same data as a function of input levels for different frequencies in sub panels. The results indicate that for normal hearing, OHC motion increased approximately linearly with input level for levels up to approximately 60-65 dB SPL. Above about 65 dB

SPL input, the output stopped increasing linearly and saturated (Fig. 2A, Fig. 3). As the input pressure increased, there was a decrease in the frequency at which maximum response was observed Fig. 1 (a, b) as shown previously [5]. There was approximately no difference between normal baseline cochlear responses and after 4 kHz tone exposure. This indicates that a 4 kHz tone exposure at a BF basal to the measurement location of 2 kHz, had approximately no effect. On the other hand, after a 2 kHz tone exposure, the responses of all frequencies decreased significantly and were below the noise floor (approximately 0 dB, or 1 nm) for input levels below 80 dB SPL (Figs. 2C, 3). For input levels above 80 dB SPL, the output stayed the same or increased dramatically for lower frequencies (Fig. 3, 1500, 1594 Hz). The postmortem results were like those after the 2 kHz tone exposure, indicating this had a dramatic effect on cochlear mechanics that nearly eliminated cochlear gain.

FIGURE 2. OHC displacement in the middle-turn at ~ 2 kHz BF. Vertical axis shows displacement in dB. (re. 1 nm) as a function of input Level (SPL) and Frequency. (a) normal cochlea, (b) after applying tone exposure at 4 kHz, which did not have any considerable effect on the OHC motion. (c) after applying tone exposure at 2 kHz where the overall amplitude of the response was lower than in panel (a) for all levels and frequencies.

DISCUSSION

Our preliminary results indicate that OHC motion saturates for input levels greater than approximately 60-65 dB SPL and for all frequencies measured. This demonstrates that the displacement of a normal hearing gerbil middle turn cochlea is nearly clamped from increasing further. Furthermore, there were no signs of harmonic distortions in the noise spectrum of our vibration measurements in the gerbil middle turn (not shown).

FIGURE 3. Displacement in dB (re. 1 nm) of OHCs vs ear canal pressure in dB SPL in the middle-turn cochlea at ~2 kHz BF plotted in each sub panel for tone frequencies ranging from 1.5-3 kHz. This was for baseline normal cochlea (Before hearing loss in blue), after 4 kHz tone exposure (yellow), after a 2 kHz tone exposure (green), and Postmortem (red).

A saturation in gerbil middle turn OHC motion for 2-2.6 kHz was also observed by Meenderink et. al. [6]. However, in their case the output saturated at levels greater than approximately ~30 dB SPL, rather than our 60 dB SPL. For 0.7-1.4 kHz, they reported the classic signs of linear growth for levels less than 30 dB SPL, and compression (less than linear growth) at higher levels. Above about 60 dB SPL, their gain decreased further and had a negative slope. There was little evidence of hyper-compression in our measurements because we did not go above about 90 dB SPL input. Another important difference was that at saturation, our displacements were in the 35-40 dB range (re 1 nm), while Meenderink et. al. measured saturated levels of about 8-15 dB (also re 1 nm). Thus, our single tone measurements are more than an order of magnitude higher. These differences in OHC motions could be attributed to our use of single tones, while previous measurements were made with multi-tone 'Zwuis tone' complex consisting of well over 30 equal intensity tones with random phase. Thus, with Zwuis tone stimulation, the overall sound level was likely about 30 dB higher than any single tone, which could explain why saturation occurs at a lower input level. Lower OHC motion due to Zwuis tone signals could result in two-tone, or more appropriately multi-tone, suppression effects resulting in lower output.

Figure 4. (A) Blue solid lines show an example of input-vs-output (I/O) curve used in some hearing aid fitting strategies with linear gain below 90 dB SPL input and peak clipping at higher levels. The dashed orange line shows a possible revised strategy based on present measurements where peak clipping starts at a lower input level of 60 dB SPL. (B) Insertion gains corresponding to panel (A).

Hearing aids use different amplification strategies, and one such strategy is linear amplification at low levels with peak clipping at higher levels [1]. The threshold for peak clipping is typically chosen to be somewhere in the 90 dB SPL input region (Figure 4). Our preliminary data suggests that the peak clipping for the I/O curve could be reduced to a lower level of 60 dB SPL, which is also illustrated in Figure 4. One caveat here is that we don't know if such a saturation occurs in humans for the low frequency apical region. Peak clipping circuits are known to result in harmonic distortions in the output and thus some caution is needed. Soft clipping help minimize some of these distortions. How the cochlea achieves saturation in OoC displacement output without measurable harmonic distortions remains a mystery.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Yi-Wen Liu]: Nice design of the experiments! I wonder, fundamentally/theoretically, whether it is possible to restore the excitation pattern of a pure tone along the cochlea after a severe hearing damage is introduced, such as described in this experiment. If on-frequency hearing is reduced while off-frequency hearing is not affected, does that indicate the excitation pattern is broadened? I will be very much impressed if one can undo the broadening via signal processing.

[Ahsan Cheema]: Thank you for your insightful comments and feedback. In these preliminary measurements, the 2 kHz damaging tone we used was too high in level resulting in profound hearing loss. In the future we plan to titrate the dosage to reduce the damage and then analyze effects such as a broadening of tuning and restoration with acoustic amplification.

[Wei-Ching Lin]: It's nice to see the in vivo vibration measurements on cochlea with hearing loss. I appreciate the experimental design. I just have a few questions and suggestions for you to consider: (1) In abstract, you wrote "*We measured organ of Corti response at the gerbil 2 kHz region for the normal ear, with noise damage, and after amplification.*" In introduction, you wrote "*The displacement responses before hearing loss, after hearing loss and postmortem were compared.*" But in result session, it seems that only vibration measured before and after hearing loss were shown and compared. Can you make the description more coherent? (2) In method part, you mentioned you choose to only include the data points 6 dB above the noise floor. Does that mean the noise floor of displacement? What's your typical scale of noise floor? (3) Can you include the result figures? (4) Can you provide the estimated scale of additional gain you need to add based on your measurements? Is that feasible?

[Ahsan Cheema]: Thank you for your questions. (1) The manuscript was revised to discuss the four different experimental conditions including the postmortem data. We did not explicitly measure with amplification but rather infer what type of amplification might be required. (2) The noise floor in the present measurements ranged from about 0 dB (re 1 nm) to -10 dB (re. 1nm). The SNR criteria of 6 dB was chosen such that the displacement was at least 6 dB higher than the noise at any given frequency. (3) Results for all four experimental conditions are now included. (4) According to these results (Fig. 3), one needs to provide 45-65 dB gain to restore the motion of cochlea at low input levels. However, such high-level gains are not prescribed by most hearing aids because it would result in noisy output. Instead, hearing aids typically use a half-gain rule that would result in 23-33 dB gain for levels below about 50 dB SPL input. For higher input levels, our preliminary results indicate that the output should saturate (Figure 4).